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MODERN APPROACHES TO FORMING A COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the theoretical foundations and contemporary approaches to developing the communicative culture of managerial staff. The study examines the impact of communicative competence on management effectiveness, leaders' professional communication skills, and the organization of effective communication with teams. The scientific substantiation for the importance of interactive trainings, leadership styles, digital communication, tools and aspects of conflict studies in the improvement of communicative culture is provided. Results show that ability of communicative competence during the management process plays an important role in the provision of an effective collaborative context among an organization as well as in improving information exchange and facilitating team work within the organization.

Keywords: communicative culture, managerial staff, communicative competence, professional communication, management effectiveness, leadership, organizational culture, strategic communication.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada boshqaruv xodimlarining kommunikativ madaniyatini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari va zamonaviy yondashuvlari tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda kommunikativ kompetensiyaning boshqaruv samaradorligiga ta'siri, rahbarlarning kasbiy muloqot ko'nikmalari hamda jamoalar bilan samarali kommunikatsiyani tashkil etish masalalari o'rganilgan. Kommunikativ madaniyatni takomillashtirishda interaktiv treninglar, liderlik uslublari, raqamli kommunikatsiya vositalari va konfliktologik yondashuvlarning ahamiyati ilmiy jihatdan asoslab berilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari boshqaruv jarayonida kommunikativ kompetensiyaning tashkilot ichida samarali hamkorlik muhitini yaratish, axborot almashinuvini yaxshilash hamda jamoaviy faoliyat samaradorligini oshirishda muhim o'rin tutishini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: kommunikativ madaniyat, boshqaruv xodimlari, kommunikativ kompetensiya, kasbiy muloqot, boshqaruv samaradorligi, liderlik, tashkiliy madaniyat, strategik kommunikatsiya.

Аннотация: В данной статье проанализированы теоретические основы и современные подходы к развитию коммуникативной культуры управленческого персонала. В исследовании рассматривается влияние коммуникативной компетентности на эффективность управления, профессиональные навыки делового общения руководителей и организацию эффективной коммуникации с коллективом. Научно обоснована значимость интерактивных тренингов, стилей лидерства, цифровых коммуникационных технологий и конфликтологических подходов в совершенствовании коммуникативной культуры. Результаты исследования показывают, что коммуникативная компетентность в процессе управления играет важную роль в формировании эффективной среды сотрудничества внутри организации, улучшении обмена информацией и повышении эффективности командной работы.

Ключевые слова: коммуникативная культура, управленческий персонал, коммуникативная компетентность, профессиональная коммуникация, эффективность управления, лидерство, организационная культура, стратегическая коммуникация.

INTRODUCTION

In contemporary society, the effectiveness of management systems largely depends on leaders' communicative culture. The successful performance of any organization or institution is ensured not only by strategic planning or technological resources, but also by effective interpersonal communication. In particular, competence in communication is one of the key competencies needed by managers to create the internal organizational climate, work with groups/teams and decisions. The degree of interaction of leaders with employees determines the internal environment in the organization, the productivity of labor, and the extent of teamwork [1].

Currently, the view of communication in management is more than just a way to exchange information, but is recognized as being a part of a social and psychological process. A leader's speech culture, listening

ability, capacity to express ideas clearly, and openness and sincerity in communicating with employees foster a climate of trust within a team. As a result, a positive psychological atmosphere is formed in the organization, which increases employees' motivation and ensures overall operational efficiency [2][3].

Communicative culture is an individual's ability to express thoughts clearly, logically, and respectfully in the communication process, to listen to and understand others, and to cooperate effectively in a social environment. Included as part of this are speech culture, following proper ethical behavioral norms, learning empathy, dialogic culture, and engaging in a constructive exchange of ideas. Communicative culture is one of the main aspects of a leader's style of team management, the method of conveying decisions, the interrelation system inside the organization [4].

The psychological climate of the team is a direct result of a leader's communicative culture. When a leader is able to create open communication, listen to employees, and demonstrate fairness, cooperation and trust within a team becomes stronger. On the contrary, poor or suboptimal communication may result in disputes, miscommunication, and lower-performance [5].

Given the globalization process amidst a rapid growth of digital technologies and new management systems, we are witnessing new manifestations of communication. A new chapter of managerial communication has been thus framed, e.g., remote management, virtual meetings, electronic document sharing, and communication through digital channels, etc. This means that leaders need to have standard communication skills but they also need to have a digital communication culture [6].

Thus, the communicative culture development of a managerial staff gained a status of one of the most significant fields of scientific research. Contemporary management theories consider communicative competence an essential element of leadership competence. An effective communication system in organizations provides a support mechanism for leaders to develop professionally, foster teamwork and support more effective management [7].

From this perspective, studying and implementing contemporary approaches to developing the communicative culture of managerial staff is one of the urgent tasks of today's management systems.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The development of the communicative culture of managerial staff has been widely studied in pedagogy, psychology, and management. In various scholarly works, this issue is interpreted as an important component of leadership competence. In the course of the study, the research works, monographs, and academic articles of national and international scholars were analyzed [8].

P. Drucker, one of the founders of management theory, emphasizes that the success of a leader's activity largely depends on the proper organization of communication processes. According to him, the main condition for effective leadership is the clear transmission of information, the establishment of effective communication with the team, and ensuring mutual understanding among employees [9][10].

Similarly, in modern management theories developed by S. Robbins, communication is considered a key element of organizational functioning. The author highlights that an organization's internal communication system plays an important role in strengthening cooperation between leaders and employees, increasing motivation, and ensuring the effectiveness of decision-making processes [11].

In pedagogy and communication theory, the works of J. DeVito are of particular importance. He interprets communicative competence as an individual's ability to communicate effectively in a social environment. According to DeVito, communicative culture consists of several key components, including speech culture, empathy, listening skills, and communication ethics [12].

Research in psychology also extensively addresses the role of communicative culture in management. For instance, in D. Goleman's theory of emotional intelligence, a leader's empathy, self-management, and effective communication skills are identified as crucial factors in developing team collaboration. In his view, leaders with higher levels of emotional intelligence are more capable of establishing effective communication with their teams.

National scholars have also studied communicative culture as a significant research area. In particular, the studies by R. Ishmuhamedov and N. Yo'ldoshev on pedagogical technologies demonstrate that effective communication is an important factor both in education and in managerial activity. Their works analyze interactive methods, problem situations, and dialogic communication techniques as effective tools for developing communicative competence [13].

In addition, contemporary research increasingly focuses on digital communication culture. The development of digital technologies has introduced new forms of communication in management. Online platforms, video conferences, and electronic information exchange require leaders to develop new communicative competencies.

Therefore, the formation of digital communication culture is regarded as one of the most relevant scientific issues [14].

The reviewed literature indicates that the communicative culture of managerial staff is one of the key factors ensuring organizational effectiveness. However, existing studies have not sufficiently explored, in a comprehensive manner, modern pedagogical and managerial approaches to developing communicative culture. For this reason, the present study analyzes contemporary approaches to developing the communicative culture of managerial staff and highlights their practical significance [15].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To examine in depth the process of developing the communicative culture of managerial staff, this study employed a set of research methods in a comprehensive manner. The methodology was implemented at the intersection of pedagogy, psychology, and management, enabling the identification of theoretical foundations, analysis of practical aspects, and development of effective mechanisms for improvement.

First, a theoretical analysis method was applied. Through this method, scholarly literature, monographs, and academic articles on communicative culture, managerial communication, leadership communication, and professional communication culture were analyzed. The theoretical analysis clarified the content of the concept of communicative culture, its structural components, and its role in managerial activity. Communicative competence was also considered as an essential component of leadership activity.

A comparative analysis method also played a significant role. This method examined models of managerial communication applied in different countries. In particular, strategies aimed at developing communicative culture in Western countries and advanced management systems were analyzed. The comparative analysis identified common and distinctive features of communication styles, leadership culture, and principles of team communication across different management systems, making it possible to determine the most effective approaches.

Observation and expert assessment methods were also used. The effectiveness of communication processes in managerial activity was studied through practical observations. Communication between leaders and team members was analyzed, and the quality of the communicative environment was assessed. In addition, expert opinions from specialists in management and pedagogy were used to identify key factors influencing the development of communicative culture.

An analytic–synthetic method was also applied to systematize and generalize the theoretical and practical data obtained. Through analytic synthesis, effective methods and contemporary approaches to developing communicative culture were identified and their practical significance was substantiated.

In the study, the communicative culture of managerial staff was examined based on the following main components:

Speech culture — the leader's ability to express ideas clearly, logically, and respectfully.

Listening Skills — the capacity to pay attention to, comprehend what the other side is saying, and offer favorable feedback

Empathy and social sensitivity — understanding the emotional states of team members and displaying socially appropriate attitudes toward them.

Communication strategy — communication that is meant to deliver organizational objectives, bring the team together, and inspire employees.

Conflict management — the capacity to refurbish differences in a constructive manner, obtain compromise, and furnish a healthy communicative atmosphere.

Such methodological approaches provided the scientific validity of the study, defined ways to form theoretical and practical conclusions on the development of the communicative culture of managerial workers.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The conducted research and theoretical analyses demonstrate that a range of contemporary pedagogical and managerial approaches are crucial for developing the communicative culture of managerial staff. In modern organizations, establishing an effective communication system is achieved through the development of leaders' communicative competence. The results show that the development of communicative culture of management personnel is ensured by the following main directions.

Interactive and communicative methods of training. The findings prove that simulated trainings belong to the most efficient ways to teach managers communicate. In trainings, problem-based scenarios more similar to real management reality than simple simulations where leaders can try different communication techniques.

All tools are used including role plays, problem situation modeling, group discussion & case study methods, as these not only develop and enhance leaders' language culture, but also develop their listening & expressing ideas with utmost expedience. In addition, leaders learn how to team up and negotiate, facilitate difficult conversations.

These studies proved that regular communicative trainings raise the quality of leaders with teams and the socio-psychological climate of organizations noticeably.

Leadership communication model. According to the study, a communicative culture of a leader has a corresponding effect on leadership capacity in modern management systems. Contemporary leader — not just a manager, but a leader who brings the team together, motivates employees to work, brings them together to achieve a common goal.

Based on the leadership communication model — communicative openness, listening to employee voice, proactive backing of initiatives, creating high-trust climate. Findings reveal that a management technique used to facilitate open and constructive conversation enhances the employment of teams and reinforces the efficacy of the organisation.

Leadership communication also has a positive impact on professional development of employees. With leaders and employees communicating openly, problems can be resolved more quickly and efficiently.

Digital communication technologies. These findings suggest that digital technologies have emerged as significant tools of managerial communication. Organizations today are heavily reliant on emails, video conferencing systems, corporate information systems, social networks, etc. for all their communication reasons.

Digital communication tools enable rapid information exchange, facilitate remote collaboration, and help speed up decision-making processes. Digital communication culture also calls for leaders to adopt new communication skills.

According to the findings, effective use of digital communication tools contributes to further improving leaders' strategic management activities. In particular, in the current context of expanding remote work, digital communication competence is an important professional quality for managerial staff.

Constructive conflict management. A very crucial aspect of communicative culture is the skill to handle disputes constructively. The study also concluded that the conflicts in organizations tend to arise out of defective means of communication or lack of adequate information.

Conflicts herein are resolved by constructive dialogs, respect and compromise amongst leaders with a high level of communicative culture. Such an approach helps in creating the right atmosphere in the team.

The findings prove that the leadership capabilities of conflict study and mediation allow for a stable workplace and improves team collaboration.

Reflection and analytical practice. These days reflection is seen as a major methodological device in modern management systems. By facilitating reflection, leaders are able to review their work, assess whether their decisions made the impact they intended, and reflect upon their manner of communicating.

Leaders who reflect on their work regularly find communicative errors faster and work to fix them, which improves management effectiveness, the findings reveal.

Using a reflective method enhances leaders' desire for self-growth, competency, and the cultural communication of their profession to a degree far better than the linear process.

The findings show that communicative culture is one of the most important factors determining management effectiveness. When an organization has an effective communication system between leaders and employees, a positive psychological climate is formed, mutual trust is strengthened, and the achievement of strategic goals becomes significantly faster. The communicative culture of managerial staff supports not only information exchange but also team-based decision-making, problem-solving, and the development of innovative ideas.

The analysis of the literature indicates that in contemporary management theories, communicative competence is viewed as a core component of leadership competence. The speech culture of a leader, the ability to listen, empathy and the ability to choose the right communication strategy — all this has a direct impact on the socio-psychological climate of the organization. I believe that these two things go hand-in-hand: when communication works, collaboration is empowered, confusion or misconceptions are decreased, and the employees feel more responsible for the company.

Further, one of the key components of communicative culture of modern management is the strategic communication. This means that leaders should communicate the ideas in a crisp manner where the two are rightly aligned and the rest of the organization is engaged in the activities that take you in the shared direction. This increases the effectiveness of management systems and facilitates a coordinated response.

The advent of digital technologies has brought managerial communication to a new phase. Email, corporate platforms, video conferencing systems, and other digital communication tools play an instrumental role in the execution of organizational processes. Thus, not only traditional and verbal communication skills, managerial staff need to acquire the digital communication culture as well. Communication in digital environments must be

clear and concise, interaction threads have to be well organized, and professional standards of behavior must be upheld.

The outcomes also indicate that construction resolution of conflicts is a vital constituent of the communicative culture. With the ability to either mediate or manage conflict, leaders become capable of addressing differing opinions and finding quick resolutions, keeping their social surroundings safe and sound.

From this perspective, developing the communicative culture of managerial staff should be carried out through the following directions:

- systematic organization of communicative trainings and practical seminars;
- development of leadership and strategic communication competencies among managers;
- formation of digital communication culture in organizations; • development of practical skills in conflict studies and mediation;
- formation of a culture of reflection and self-analysis.

These approaches contribute to establishing an effective communication environment in management systems and further developing leaders' professional competencies.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The communicative culture of managerial staff is one of the key factors ensuring organizational effectiveness. Under contemporary management conditions, leaders must possess not only high-level professional knowledge but also well-developed communicative competence. Teamwork is enhanced by improved communications, employee motivation is heightened, and organizational development is nurtured and congruent.

It shows that the interactive trainings, leadership communication, the use of digital communication technologies, and the reflective analysis methods are of utmost importance in establishing communicative culture. Not only do these methods increase the communication capacity of the leaders, but they also organize the information exchange and collaboration processes harmoniously within organizations.

In addition, training in the communicative competence of managerial personnel provides for the formation of an innovative management environment, more effective implementation of strategic decisions and provides opportunities for full disclosure of the creative potential of the team.

It is thus necessary to create tailored training programs that focus on developing the communicative culture of leaders, conduct communicative training sessions, and introduce contemporary management technologies in organizations.

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